

PREVENTION OF DISPUTES BETWEEN TEACHERS AND STUDENTS

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Abstract: This scientific article describes opinions on the prevention of misunderstandings and conflicts between teachers and students in the educational system. Also, the positive and negative aspects of this situation for the quality of education are revealed.

Key words: Educational process, educational quality efficiency, problem and conflict, methodology.

In order to become a true master of each direction, a person must have natural abilities, certain physical and mental reforms, thorough training, personal preparation and certain personal qualities. What kind of relationships should we pay attention to when directing to the pedagogical goal. A person who chooses the profession of pedagogy must first be healthy, be able to pronounce words correctly and well, be calm and composed, and be able to control oneself in dealings with others. Also, the presence of personal qualities such as liking children, willingness to work with them confidently, politeness, broad-mindedness, organization, and demandingness towards oneself and others also indicate a person's suitability for pedagogical work.

In order to achieve his goal, the pedagogue should have the following qualities in order to enter into a relationship with students. Love of children and interest in working with them, love of pedagogical work, psychological and pedagogical acumen and observation, organizational ability, truthfulness, sincerity, demandingness, determination and striving for a goal, self-control. A teacher should be able to pay special attention to character traits of students in the process of pedagogical goal-oriented attitude.

Working together to achieve the goal. In the field of education, we will achieve the goal. We must strive together. The employees who organize education are pedagogues, so it is appropriate to work together with them for the effective implementation of education. It is known that in order to achieve the goal in the pedagogical profession, it is not enough for the teacher to be knowledgeable, to have deep knowledge of this or that subject. A teacher is also education. It is necessary for him to know to what extent and with what methods to learn a subject, taking into account the age and mental characteristics of children, the methods of educating children, and the laws of the formation of a human personality.

The pedagogue knows how to work with the team, the same treatment in the process of responding to the group's demands, working with parents is an integral part of the work system of the group leader. Working with parents requires gentleness, patience, consistent and strict attention of the pedagogue to establish a reliable and working relationship with them. The general and tasks of education are successfully solved through the parents' team. If the head of the class warns the parents by forcing them to work individually with the students who have difficulty in education, they will not face difficulties in achieving the goal.

The teacher's negative attitudes, the mistakes made by the teacher in the evaluation of the students' knowledge, the mistakes made in the evaluation lead not only to the change of the evaluation components, but also to the change of the entire learning activity. They reinforce the flaws inherent in this system, making it inferior or unattractive. Positive results were obtained, compared with the student himself. It is necessary to compare children's knowledge in such a way that it supports children to achieve the best results and improve their personality, without lifting someone up and putting others down. A teacher should pay attention to the character of each student in order to prevent conflicts and contradictions. Pedagogy should be able to overcome teacher's conflicts so that conflicts, conflicts, confrontations do not arise between pedagogues and students. In a modern way, we need to find the right solution for our conflict management.

Our society is wide-ranging and we can meet people of different characters there. Interpersonal conflicts are definitely manifested in activities. For example, we will see in the example of a group. Imagine we have talented individuals in one group. They are able to express their independent opinions by mastering each content well, and due to the wide range of opinions, conflicts, major disagreements and conflicts arise between them. Each group member can prove the correctness of his opinion, in such cases, conflict management is eliminated by the teacher. We can see conflicts between individuals in every field. If people work on themselves, can they prove their point, they will also find solutions to conflicts.

Boredom from any activity is possible, but a person does not get tired of communication, especially its informal, sincere, direct form, good interlocutors are always spiritually stimulated. In fact, the social experience of each person, his human image, qualities, and even defects are the product of communication processes. The elementary function of any communication is to ensure that the

interlocutors understand each other. In order to prevent pedagogical conflicts, one person speaks, the other equalizes and listens. The effectiveness of communication depends on the compatibility and complementarity of these two aspects. One of the misconceptions is that when a person is taught to interact or communicate, he should only be taught to speak and use logically based words. They teach to speak secretly. His second side, listening ability, is not given much attention. When the famous American speaker and psychologist Dale Carnegie said that "a good conversationalist is not a conversationalist who knows how to speak well, but a conversationalist who knows how to listen well", he meant the development of these skills in people.

The teacher communicates with people - young children - who are just entering life and are forming as a complete person. As a result of some random behavior of the teacher, the opinion of the students about him can have a negative effect on the educational process and complicate the work of the teacher. Usually, such conflicts last a long time and are resolved in favor of the teacher. In order to protect the teacher's reputation, adults sometimes destroy the student's dignity and demand forgiveness from the student, although the reason for this conflict was the teacher's wrong behavior. The teacher's work does not meet the requirements of moral education. It is necessary to approach each of them individually in dealing with children. If the teacher and student listen to each other, they will educate themselves. So, the process of listening is not as passive as many people imagine. The ability to listen inspires the speaker, inspires him, creates an opportunity for the formation of new ideas.

Sincerity is one of the best and noble qualities of a person, we often do not pay attention to the meaning of this word, which is used almost every day. In fact, when we translate the words "sincerity" and "sincerity" into Uzbek, the meanings "one who can be like-minded and listen to others, aware" come out. Sincerity, which is one of the virtues known as morality, is a big dream. Sincerity appears in the interaction and communication of people. How many people communicate with each other every day. What is the difference between sincere and open-mindedness? Your Excellency, people are equal, big and small, they strive to earn their living, support the truth, strive for enlightenment, and respect themselves. In the process of dealing with children, if we use the right words, volunteerism, tolerance, knowledge, impartiality, the young generation we are raising will develop high qualities. We should teach children to do good, to show virtue, to greet, to respect adults, to show respect to children, and to form feelings of love.

As a conclusion, we can say that our ancestors always lived with good intentions, good dreams, and tried to leave behind good children, good students, good poets, and a good name. Only good people can do good to people. Children should be taught noble attitudes: love for the motherland, piety, fortitude, virtue, courage, patience, conscience, modesty, chastity, loyalty, friendship, humility, words, courage, humanity, hard work, truthfulness, asking the right question. It is our pedagogue's and parents' duty to inculcate such qualities in their minds during the educational process.

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